

The Conservation History and Treatment of Three Large-Scale Paintings by Joan Miró: Relieving Canvas Distortions in Highly Reactive Paintings with a Gliding Elastic Tensioning System

ABSTRACT

*This article describes the treatment of three canvas paintings by Joan Miró, measuring approximately 366 × 347 cm, exhibited as a triptych with the title *Peintures Murales pour un Temple* (1962). The three paintings were executed on sized, open-weave linen canvas. The paintings have undergone extensive and intrusive early restorations in an attempt to prevent cracking, flaking paint, and planar distortions. During previous treatments, additional animal glue was applied to the versos of the canvases, causing them to become even more reactive to the wide environmental changes they are subjected to.*

All previous attempts at treating the paintings were unsuccessful, including the 2006 restretching of the Red painting onto a continuous tension Starofix stretcher. Upon the invitation of a private collection in March 2013, Luca Bonetti Corp. teamed up with Equilibrarte to use a spring-loaded stretcher to stabilize the reactive paintings by freeing them along their perimeters. A custom-made edge lining, designed by Equilibrarte, was used to allow for movement of the canvas perpendicular to the edge. The tensioning system allowed avoiding the use of tacks or staples, thus highly reducing damage and stresses when mounting and unmounting large canvas paintings. The force is measured on the springs, which are more yielding than the painting. The treatment involved environmental monitoring and frequent condition assessment of the paintings. It was concluded with a thorough revision after 5 years, including minor adjustments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Joan Miró's three paintings, *Peinture Murale I Jaune Orange* (18 May 1962), *Peinture Murale II Verte* (21 May 1962), and *Peinture Murale III Rouge* (22 May 1962) were completed in May 1962. Each painting approximately measures 366 × 347 cm, and the group is intended and exhibited as a triptych with the title *Peintures Murales pour un Temple* (fig. 1). In this article, the individual paintings will be referred to as the Orange, Green, and Red paintings, respectively.

The paintings are extremely reactive to changes in relative humidity and temperature as a result of the materials and techniques used for their manufacturing. During periods of relative humidity greater than 55%, the paintings exhibited severe slackness and planar distortions. During periods of relative humidity lower than 25%, the paintings exhibited major constrictions that caused severe warping of the stretchers and frames, pulling opposing corners away from the wall up to distances of 25 cm (fig. 2).

Miró painted on open-weave canvases that were originally sized using a large amount of animal glue. The glue sealed

the interstices between the threads, forming a continuous film on the face of the canvas, what is now made evident by the absence of the gesso ground in the interstices of the weave on the reverse. The presence of a strong sizing and a glue-bound ground has made the paintings so reactive to relative humidity variations. This could explain why the paintings began to undergo numerous conservation and restoration interventions soon after their completion, due to flaking, cracking, and severe planar distortions.

The first intervention occurred less than 10 years after their execution and seemed to be responding to an emergency. A technician, with permission from the artist, treated them for visible signs of instability and flaking. Documentation indicates the treatment involved applying a thick layer of animal glue to the reverse of the canvas in hopes of consolidating the flaking paint. Weave impressions and moating visible around areas of impasto are visible on the surfaces of the paintings and suggest ironing from the reverse—another possible vestige from this early intervention. With this treatment, the extreme planar distortions mentioned previously began to be noted in documentation.

Figure 1. The three paintings composing the triptych.

The paintings were purchased in 1980. Several treatments were sought for the large-scale paintings in the hopes of controlling their extreme reactions to environmental changes and the related recurring damages. The recent conservation treatments described in this article started in 2006, when Luca Bonetti Corp. mounted the Red painting on a Starofix stretcher with spring-loaded corner expansion. Following several exhibitions, it became apparent that the Starofix stretcher was not adequate in responding to extreme environmental fluctuations and the painting needed additional treatment. In March 2013, Luca Bonetti Corp. teamed up with Equilibrarte to use a gliding elastic tensioning system to stabilize the reactive paintings. The system involved the use of a custom-made edge lining connected to springs that allow for the unimpeded expansion and contraction of the canvas. The main difference from other elastic systems is that the painting is not stapled or otherwise fixed on the perimeter of the stretcher but, on the contrary, allowed to move freely across and around it. Springs are able to develop less force than the painting is, implying that they will always act as a stress release and not as a constraint element.

2. HISTORY OF THE PAINTINGS AND PREVIOUS INTERVENTIONS

Previous treatment reports, proposals, and discussions between the conservators and curator of the collection have provided an approximate history of the paintings before their current ownership. Although there exist gaps in the chronology of the paintings, it is clear that there have been numerous interventions. Treatment proposals written in the past 20 years also provide clues to previous condition issues and the ongoing issue of severe planar distortions.

2.1 The Paintings before Current Ownership

Based on the inscription by the artist on the reverse of all three canvases, they were completed between May 18 and 23, 1962. Most of what is known about the paintings' histories comes from a letter from Galerie Maeght to the collector at the time of their acquisition. The letter, written in 1980, includes an account from a French restorer, Jean-Paul Ledeur, who described previous restoration work completed by technicians under the supervision of Miró, 10 to 15 years before. He stated that "each work was mounted on a stretcher which was structurally weak, resulting in buckling and deformation. The backs of the canvas were treated a relatively long time ago (10–15 years). This treatment was applied as a result of the fact that the pigment and the sizing of the canvas did not completely adhere to the canvas itself. It was therefore necessary to reapply them from behind in order not to lose the Artist's work." Ledeur

Figure 2. The paintings draped above 60%RH and contracted so badly in dry conditions that stretchers and frames warped off the wall.

suggested that a technician, possibly under Miró's guidance, applied a protein glue to the backs of the paintings. He also suggested that Miró painted over large portions of the canvas, stating "a halo, created by the Artist's work in the background, is visible." Ledeur's own work consisted of building more suitable stretchers, loose lining the canvases, restretching the paintings over the new stretchers, light cleaning, and a few "touch-ups." According to his notes, the Green painting appeared to have been flaking, as he states "our work consisted primarily of painstaking refixing of the green pigment onto the white base."

2.2 The Paintings in the Collection

In the files recording correspondence since the time of acquisition, there are few documents that describe the condition of the paintings before 1990. The paintings were lent to the National Gallery of Art in Washington, DC, in 1990 for the 10th anniversary of the East Building. Before they traveled for the exhibition, they were treated by Daniel Goldreyer, who removed a dent and "neutralized and removed water stains, runs, mildew, scuff, oxidation, etc." Soon after the date of his initial treatment report, more condition reports and extensive proposals for each painting

appeared, in which he stated that all three exhibited extreme buckling and distortions and proposed to "infuse the priming in cracked and blistered areas, as necessary, restretch and stabilize the canvas, and restore water-damaged areas." He most probably treated all three paintings in accordance with his proposals, although only the treatment receipt for the Orange painting could be found.

At some point in their history, the paintings were rolled. The Orange painting exhibits a repeating craquelure pattern that suggests it was dented while rolled. The cracks were treated with what appears to be an epoxy resin, applied locally in thick blocks on the reverse. The epoxy pre-dates the 1990 Goldreyer condition reports, as he included them in a drawing made on the reverse.

In 2006, the Red painting was treated by Luca Bonetti Corp. with the main goal of resolving the warping and planar distortions of the paintings. It was found that the paintings had been glued directly to the wooden stretchers with what appeared to be a polyvinyl acetate (PVA)-type adhesive. The original tacking margins were damaged and overpainted. During treatment, the painting was removed from the

stretcher and old PVA adhesive was reduced around the edges, a new edge lining was provided (linen and BEVA 371), and the painting was stretched over an aluminum Starofix stretcher. Starofix stretchers apply continuous tension through a spring-loaded corner expansion system. The tensioning system implies that the painting is fixed to the edges of movable corners, but unfortunately this degree of freedom proved to be insufficient for the highly reactive paintings, causing the undulations and planar distortions to reappear during periods of high relative humidity (fig. 3).

In 2011, the three paintings were on display in the exhibition *Miró: The Ladder of Escape* and traveled to the Tate Modern in London, the Fundació Joan Miró in Barcelona, and the National Gallery of Art in Washington, DC. During the

traveling exhibition, the paintings reacted differently to changing environmental conditions. The corner movements allowed stress release for the Red painting during periods of low relative humidity: although the Orange and Green paintings warped significantly, the Red remained in plane. However, during periods of high relative humidity, all three paintings exhibited sag and distortions because the spring-loaded movement of the corners could not provide the needed tension to the painting fixed along the perimeter.

3. APPLYING A GLIDING ELASTIC TENSION SYSTEM

Following the 2011 exhibition, it was clear that the treatment of the Red painting was unsuccessful in controlling the

Figure 3. The Red painting sagging in high relative humidity after being mounted on the Starofix stretcher.

distortions of the canvas. In 2013, Luca Bonetti Corp. teamed with Equilibrarte, a conservation studio in Rome specializing in structural treatments and in the custom building of spring-loaded strainers, to retreat the paintings, starting with the Red.

3.1 An Overview of Spring-Loaded Tensioning Systems

When a stretcher is expanded with the keys, the only part of the painting to receive tension is that close to the corners. The rest of the canvas is fixed to the stretcher bars, and the tacks or nails do not allow any displacement of the canvas. This uneven distribution of stresses causes overstretching of the canvas and eventually the displacement of the keys, which tend to fall out of their slots. Spring-loaded tensioning systems for paintings were first developed in the second half of the 19th century,¹ as a direct response to the issues of the corner expansion stretcher with keys. Spring-loaded corner movement was intended to eliminate the need for manual adjustment of tension and the other problems related to the keys.

Unfortunately, all of these systems develop a strong friction between the moving elements in the corners, and springs need to be strong to produce the movement. In addition, the springs have limited space within the wooden corners and need to be short and stiff (fig. 4). Such a configuration results in a cyclic expansion of the stretcher when painting materials lose tension. Many painful examples are known in the conservation history of US paintings, when self-expanding stretchers tear the canvas along the perimeter, starting from the corners.²

The Starofix stretcher used for the Red painting has better control of the friction of the moving elements in the corners

and has soft enough springs to allow the release of tension when the painting contracts (Bonetti 1999). This design avoids the dangers of the earlier models, but blocking the painting on the perimeter can clearly create other problems.

A completely different approach underpins the stretcher design started in 1954 in Rome at the Central Institute of Restoration when two Caravaggio paintings (*St. Jerome Writing* and the large *Beheading of St. John the Baptist*) from Malta underwent restoration. The paintings were stretched on strainers with rounded profiles. The excess lining canvas was allowed to turn over the edge of the strainers and was connected to springs attached to the crossbars (Carità 1957). They were freed on the perimeter and could adjust their dimensions without buckling, as springs attached to the canvas margins, instead of tack or staples, allowed for their natural movements. The developer of this innovation, Roberto Carità, was also the first to publish the value of force (tension) considered acceptable for a painting. For fragile detached wall paintings mounted on canvas, he used the very gentle force of 1.36 N/cm. However, for canvas paintings, paste lined with a double linen canvas like the Caravaggios, Carità (1955) stated that a much higher force could be used.³

The tensioning system became a standard for the canvas paintings treated at the Central Institute of Restoration until 1960, when Carità left the institute. In 1989, after the *St. Jerome* was stolen, the method got new attention and was analyzed by Accardo et al. (1991) using finite element analysis of the distribution of tensions, showing how it allowed avoiding stress concentrations in the corners and on tacking margins (Accardo et al. 1992). The updated approach resulted in specifications that springs should be as soft as possible (Nimmo et al. 1996). It also became clear that the original stretchers/strainers could be reused, with minor modifications, as the structure around which the tensioning system was built. In 1993, the method was used for the first time on the original strainer of a 17th-century painting, with the value of tension of 2.55 N/cm. This was much lower than in the past despite the fact that the painting was paste lined with a double linen canvas just like the *St. Jerome*⁴ (Iaccarino 1996).

Extensive research carried out from 2000 to 2004 allowed investigation of the relationship existing between the painting's behavior and its tension on the stretcher (Iaccarino Idelson 2004, 2009). Among the most relevant results was the definition of the value of "maximum useful tension" at around 2.5 N/cm. The concept is easily described by the fact that when a force is applied on the plane of the painting, the maximum useful tension value is a threshold after which tension shows a decreasing influence on the painting's ability to resist to the deformation (fig. 5).

Figure 4. The 1866 corner expansion elastic stretcher patented by J. E. Todd.

Figure 5. Maximum useful tension is the threshold value after which tension reduces its influence on the painting's response to an external pressure.

Between 2004 and 2007, a survey showed that 106 mid-career and senior conservators chose the average tension of 1.8 N/cm for the same mockup of an unlined painting.⁵

3.2 The Tensioning System Designed for the Miró Paintings

The tensioning system was composed of stainless steel springs connected to the painting through stainless steel rods inserted into pockets sewn into the edge lining. The rods were connected to the springs via stainless steel wires turning on small pulleys for a better use of the space (fig. 6).

The painting was allowed to move freely over the edges of the strainer, with tubes rolling on ball bearings. Tubes (16 mm in diameter) rotate when the painting slides along the strainer perimeter and changes dimensions, allowing for virtual elimination of friction in the main component of movement. The ball bearings are fixed on custom-designed laser-cut stainless steel plates (fig. 7).

The springs⁶ were set to work with a force that was far below their yield point to avoid mechanical deterioration. Nevertheless, the springs are soft enough to allow the

painting to be always stronger, in any environmental condition. When the painting experiences dimensional changes due to environmental conditions, the overall force does not change much because the springs' elastic constant is low. The force being the product of the elongation and the elastic constant,⁷ its changes are small as the constant is low, with values remaining close to the numbers of the initial installation. The level of tension was chosen not only for maintaining the paintings' planarity. It was also a level deemed suitable for avoiding new crack formation and any other tension-related damages in the paintings. In accordance with the research described previously, in June 2014 the value of tension was set at 2.1 N/cm, lower than the maximum useful tension. It was chosen on the high side of the possible values because of the extreme reactivity shown by the paintings.

3.3 The Choice of the Value of Tension

Constituent materials in the paintings are all hygroscopic and change their elastic module according to their moisture content. With high relative humidity, animal glues become more yielding, as do most oil paints, whereas the canvas becomes

Figure 6. The springs mounted on the stretcher bars. Force, diverted with a pulley, acts perpendicular to the steel rod inserted in the edge lining canvas.

more resistant to traction because of the increasing hydrogen bonds within the cellulose fibers. At low relative humidity, animal glues become much stiffer (E module increases) and reduce their dimensions, developing enough force for all of the other materials to follow them (Mecklenburg 1982).

The environment was monitored over three seasonal changes showing very low relative humidity values during the heated winter period (with peaks reaching 7%RH) and higher relative humidity values during spring and summer (reaching up to 70%RH). The paintings in the Miró triptych are expected to show a dimensional variation of approximately 0.5% when submitted to extreme relative humidity changes,⁸ meaning changes of approximately 2 cm in the horizontal direction and 1.5 cm in the vertical direction.

The tensioning system responds according to the elastic constant of the springs,⁹ and therefore the variation of force

is small (0.42 N/cm in the horizontal direction and 0.32 N/cm in the vertical direction). Such a low variability of the tension from the initial value allows a high degree of confidence on the behavior of the system when critical relative humidity values are reached in the conservation environment. Still, the choice should also take into consideration material fatigue, which is the effect of the repeatedly cycling environmental conditions. Exceeding the limit of fatigue endurance of a material can lead to its failure after a certain number of cycles even though the stress does not reach its ultimate strength.¹⁰ Alain Roche (2018), in his recent book on the conservation of modern and contemporary paintings, provides a value of 0.48 N/cm as the maximum variation of force that similar paintings should be able to safely withstand over many thousands of cycles, what is safely higher than the expected maximum variations of force if no improvement of the environment conditions should be possible in the future.

Figure 7. The rolling profiles on ball bearings virtually eliminate friction on the perimeter of the stretcher.

3.4 Tensioning the Red Painting

Face down on a wooden platform, the painting was unmounted from the Starofix stretcher, and the old edge lining was removed. BEVA 371 was removed using compresses moistened with naphtha to first soften the adhesive. Remnants of the old PVA adhesive were swelled with acetone. Numerous tears and losses were treated along the tacking margins, with soluble nylon strips and patches made of thin Pecap applied with BEVA film.

As if it were an original stretcher, a new wooden strainer¹¹ was dimensioned to accommodate the rolling aluminum tubes along the outside edges of the stretcher.

A strong linen edge lining, with a pocket along the perimeter to accommodate the steel rod used in the tensioning system, was applied to the tacking margins with BEVA 371. The pocket was also sealed with the same adhesive, thus building a double layer of what was considered as a “standard” canvas for a large-format painting. Steel wires connected the rods to the springs; their length was adjusted so as to obtain a homogeneous distribution of tension with the chosen value of 2.1 N/cm.

Following restretching, the painting was protected with polyethylene backing boards inserted in the new strainer and framed to avoid any damage to the edges and tensioning system.

Surprisingly, the painting still exhibited undulations during periods of high relative humidity. After careful examination of the painting and environmental conditions, which had been monitored during and after treatment, it became clear

that the problem was caused by the presence of a too stiff edge lining. The painting had been stretched in low relative humidity conditions, although 35%RH could not be considered very dry if compared to the minimum values that the painting was exposed to. For this reason, the inextensible edge lining was locking the length of perimeter in a dimension corresponding to that of the painting in a contracted state. This proved incompatible with normal to high relative humidity conditions for such a reactive painting. The stress relaxation and increase of dimensions in animal glue and oil layers due to high relative humidity caused a similar accumulation of expanded painting experienced as when it was stapled onto the stretcher. At low relative humidity, the distortions disappeared in the same way that they had when mounted on the Starofix stretcher (see fig. 3), as glue contraction restored the dimensions the painting had when the edge lining was installed.

It became clear that the edge lining needed to be replaced to let the tensioning system work also under such extreme conditions. This was the welcome occasion for developing a new edge lining material, a specially woven¹² linen canvas with bands without warp. The fill yarns of such sections were stabilized with BEVA film and attached to the edges, allowing unrestrained expansion and contraction of the painting not only across the rolling profiles on the stretcher bars but also along them (fig. 8). The pocket was sewn in the full canvas outside the painting, housing the stainless steel rods for the connection to the springs. The change of edge lining fabric allowed free movement of the painting, and the following cycles of relative humidity saw no distortion appear on the painting.

Figure 8. The new edge lining canvas, with monodirectional (fill) threads connected to the paintings' tacking margin with BEVA film.

3.5 Tensioning the Green and Orange Paintings

After 1 year of environmental monitoring and visual observation of the Red painting, also the two other elements of the triptych were treated. The strainers were entirely built out of aluminum,¹³ allowing better performance and environmental stability with lower weight. They were equipped with the same rolling profiles, tensioning system, and backing boards (fig. 9). The paintings were housed in identical wooden frames that provided enough space to allow for the unimpeded movement of the canvases and to protect the mechanisms from handling and impact.

Following treatment, the three paintings continued to be monitored in their exhibition space, and the environmental data was collected for another year. The three paintings were equipped with wi-fi dataloggers for relative humidity and temperature, monitoring also the space protected by the backing boards.

The new tensioning system with the new edge lining has proved to be successful in maintaining the planarity of all three paintings with unchanged environmental stresses. All internal tensions were handled by the elastic system, and no distortions in either the paintings or the stretchers appeared again.

4. ASSESSMENT OF THE CONDITION OF THE PAINTINGS AFTER 5 YEARS AND CHECK OF THE TENSIONING SYSTEM

No problems appeared in the paintings over the next 5 years, and no action was necessary. In May 2019, a complete condition assessment was carried out, confirming that no new problems had arisen (fig. 10). The condition check was also the occasion to measure the springs and evaluate the evolution of the tension and the paintings' dimensions.

At the time of the assessment, environmental conditions were different (57%RH) from the moment in which tension had been last measured (38%RH). The paintings thus had different dimensions, which could be precisely measured through the springs they are connected to. The average increase in dimensions was found to be 1.8 mm in the horizontal direction and 1.1 mm in the vertical direction. In the triptych, the canvas weft unexpectedly appears to be placed in the direction of the long side of the paintings (346 cm), because the corresponding threads are of a lower quality and show lesser torsion and much more crimp, whereas the vertical ones (266 cm) are straighter and regularly spaced. This consideration implies that the manufacturer used a loom measuring at least 3.6 m for weaving the canvas, which was a rather uncommon size in

Figure 9. The stretcher of the Orange painting before the installation of the backing boards. Edge lining corners were not yet finished, and temporary supports on the bottom allowed the painting to move by keeping it off the ground.

the early 1960s. Nevertheless, the information seems to be confirmed by the slight anisotropy found in the behavior of the painting. The average strain in warp is 0.0004, whereas that of the weft is 0.0005. This seems to be in accordance with the weft's greater ability to expand.

For unlined paintings with similar structures, we generally choose a value of tension in the interval of 1.6–1.9 N/cm—that is, a gentle tension allowing the paintings to be in a planar and undistorted state, with a low value of stress on the original materials. In 2014, we had set the tension to 2.1 N/cm because of the high reactivity of the paintings, the strong distortions, and the great force they showed when twisting the wooden stretchers away from the wall.

Five years of “effortless” planarity of the paintings demonstrated that the precaution was unnecessary. We therefore decided to lower the value to the minimum deemed necessary to have a pleasant “feel” to the touch for the conservator. Nevertheless, a conservator manually evaluating the tension of a painting stretched with springs on a gliding profile strainer will need to keep in mind that no initial overstretching is necessary, as would be the case with key expansion stretchers or strainers. This is true because when the painting is free on the perimeter and is in a flowing equilibrium with soft springs, the value of tension will not decrease or go out of control with time.

The value of tension was adjusted to 1.6 N/cm: a value that satisfied the conservators in the group. However, at first the nonspecialists found it a bit hard to accept the need to change

Figure 10. The paintings mounted in their frames in the entrance hall of the building.

something that had proved to be so effective and satisfactory for the past 5 years: “if it is not broken, you don’t fix it!”

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NOTES

1. The US Patent and Trademark Office records an elastic stretcher as early as September 18, 1866: “Improvement in artist’s stretchers,” J. E. Todd [US patent 58,154].
2. For example, this happened to the painting by D. Johnson “On the Unadilla,” mounted on a Wright and Gardner stretcher in 1884. Thanks to Dorothy Mahon, the Metropolitan Museum of Art, for the information.
3. Carità (1955) states that “for a painting measuring a few square meters a force of at least one ton will be necessary.” Applying this information to the “St. Gerome reading,” the force would count some 18 N/cm.
4. Two spring types were used in different positions on the stretcher, and both had low elastic modulus (0.92 and 1.33 N/mm).
5. The survey was carried out by Antonio Iaccarino Idelson and Carlo Serino interviewing almost 200 conservators during the yearly professional meetings in different areas of Italy. Conservators had different backgrounds and years of experience. The 106 mentioned earlier were chosen for having a minimum of 15 years of experience on canvas paintings.
6. ISO 302; external diameter: 8 mm; diameter of the wire: 1.1 mm; coil length: 43 mm; average constant of elasticity: 1.02 N/mm; preload: 11 N.
7. As the force equals the elongation times the elastic constant ($F = kl$, Hooke’s law), a low elastic constant implies a small variation of force corresponds to dimensional variations.
8. The maximum dimensional variation measured in the paintings object of the study by Iaccarino Idelson (2004) is 0.5%. This figure also corresponds to the span of dimensional variation of the hide glue alone, as measured by Mecklenburg in 1982.
9. The system is composed of 17 springs and 13 springs on each of the opposite sides, horizontal and vertical, 34 and 26 per direction, with the elastic constant of 1.02 N/mm. The difference in elongation is equally divided between the two sides of each direction.
10. In materials science, fatigue is the weakening of a material caused by cyclic loading that results in progressive and localized structural damage and the growth of cracks. Once a fatigue crack has initiated, each loading cycle will grow the crack a small amount. Microscopic cracks will begin to initiate at stress concentrations such as holes, composite interfaces, or grain boundaries in metals. The stress values that cause fatigue-related damage can be much less than the ultimate tensile strength or the yield strength of the material.
11. Custom made by Simon Liu Inc.
12. By the renowned Italian company Sironi Enrico, established in 1892, Gallarate (Varese) Italy.
13. Produced in Italy by the conservation company Equilibrarte, specializing in structural conservation of paintings and cultural heritage artifacts.

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AUTHORS

ANTONIO IACCARINO IDELSON

Equilibrarte s.r.l.

E-mail: iaccarino.a@gmail.com

ANA ALBA

Alba Art Conservation

E-mail: ana.a.alba@gmail.com

LUCA BONETTI

Luca Bonetti Corp.

E-mail: lucabonetti@gmail.com

CARLO SERINO

Equilibrarte s.r.l.

E-mail: carlo.serino@gmail.com